

Effect of herbicides on weed control in transplanted rice, Kota, India.

Treatment ^a	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Grain yield		Panicles/m ²		Panicle wt (g)		Weed dry wt (g/m ²) at harvest		Cost-to-benefit ratio ^b
		(t/ha)								
		1984	1985	1984	1985	1984	1985	1984	1985	
2,4-D EE (G)	0.8	6.7	5.2	312	281	2.8	2.9	170	74	13.2
2,4D EE (G)	1.0	6.9	5.6	321	283	2.7	2.9	167	71	12.5
Oxyfluorfen (G)	0.1	6.1	5.8	311	290	3.2	2.8	190	85	–
Oxyfluorfen (G)	0.15	6.3	5.8	324	295	3.4	2.9	149	82	–
Thiobencarb (G)	1.0	6.7	5.8	320	297	2.9	3.0	188	78	14.5
Thiobencarb (G)	1.5	6.7	5.9	295	284	3.0	2.8	185	70	9.9
Anilofos (EC)	0.3	6.5	4.8	298	295	2.9	2.7	209	95	–
Anilofos (EC)	0.4	6.2	5.3	310	271	2.9	2.8	189	89	–
Butachlor (G)	1.0	6.6	5.4	290	242	3.0	3.0	192	95	12.4
Butachlor (G)	1.5	6.8	5.7	315	253	2.9	2.9	190	96	9.5
Pendimethalin (G)	1.0	7.1	6.1	332	267	3.5	3.3	130	69	18.4
Pendimethalin (G)	1.5	6.9	5.7	310	267	2.8	3.0	163	75	10.7
Butachlor (EN)	1.0	5.7	5.6	299	261	2.5	2.8	210	100	10.8
Butachlor (EN)	1.5	6.1	5.7	300	252	3.3	2.8	180	104	8.5
Hand weeding 20 and 40 DT	–	7.0	6.0	323	262	3.5	3.5	134	15	7.0
Unweeded check	–	4.6	4.0	264	236	2.4	2.3	232	166	–
CD (0.05)		0.2	0.2	3	4	0.1	0.3	2	2	–

^a EE = ethyl ester, G = granules, EC = emulsifiable concentrate, EN = emulsion. Cost of 2,4-D 4G, \$1/kg; thiobencarb 10 G, \$2.15/kg; butachlor 5G, \$1.1/kg; pendimethalin S G, \$1/kg; butachlor 50 EN, \$10/liter; oxyfluorfen and anilofos, not available. ^b Grain, \$160/t; C:B averaged over 2 yr.

Pendimethalin at 1.0 and 1.5 kg ai/ha, thiobencarb at 1.0 and 1.5 kg ai/ha, and 2,4-D at 1.0 kg ai/ha were effective in controlling weeds (see table). These treatments had significantly higher grain yield, more effective tillers, and higher panicle weight than the unweeded check. The highest benefit-to-cost ratio was with pendimethalin at 1 kg ai/ha. □

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Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Yield loss to rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae*

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We conducted two experiments with potted plants to determine yield loss to *H. oryzae*.

IR20 seedlings raised in sterile soil were transplanted 21 d after sowing at 4 seedlings/pot. Treatments were rice root nematodes inoculated at 1 and at 10/g soil and an untreated check, in 8

Effect of rice root nematode *H. oryzae* on height and yield of rice. ^a Tamil Nadu, India, 1984-85.

Treatment (nematodes/g soil)	Plant ht (cm)			Grain		Straw	
	30 DT	60 DT	At harvest	Yield (g/4 hills)	Reduction (%)	Yield (g/4 hills)	Reduction (%)
0	38 a	62 a	79 a	44.1 a	–	34.1 a	–
1	34 b	58 b	70 b	32.2 b	26.9	26.0 b	22.9
10	30 c	54 c	68 c	26.6 c	39.7	19.7 c	42.2
CD (0.05)		1		5.2	–	3.5	–

^a Mean for 2 pot experiments, with 8 replications each. DT = days after transplanting. In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

replications.

Yield losses were 27% with 1 nematode/g soil and 40% with 10

nematodes/g soil (see table). Straw yields were 23% less with 1 nematode and 42% less with 10 nematodes. □

Control of rice root nematode with carbofuran

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The effect of carbofuran on populations of rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella*

mucronata and on growth characteristics of rice were measured in microplot field experiments in 1983 and 1984 rainy seasons. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with 4 treatments and 5 replications in 16-m² subplots.

Treatments were seedlings from an untreated nursery (T1), seedlings from a

carbofuran-treated nursery (T2), seedlings from the untreated nursery with carbofuran applied 50 d after transplanting (DT) (T3), and seedlings from the carbofuran-treated nursery with carbofuran at 50 DT (T4). All applications were at 1 kg ai/ha.

Experimental field soil was loamy clay with pH 6.4. Recommended NPK